

Optimization of Standalone Hybrid Power Plant using ABC Algorithm

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Abstract: Renewable energy systems are proving to be promising and environmentfriendly sources of electricity generation, particularly, in countries with inadequate fossil fuel resources. In recent years, wind, solar photovoltaic(PV) and biomass based systems have been drawing more attention to provide electricity to isolated or energy deficient regions. Solar and windenergy systems are omnipresent, freely available, environmental friendly,and they are considered as promising power generating sources due to their availability and topological advantages for local power generations. Hybrid solar–wind energy systems, uses two renewable energy sources, allow improving the system efficiency and power reliability and reduce the energy storage requirements for stand-alone applications. The hybrid solar–wind systems are becoming popular in remote area power generation applications due to advancements in renewable energy technologies and substantial rise in prices of petroleum products.

Keywords: Renewable energy, wind energy, environmental friendly, energy storage.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rapid depletion of fossil fuel resources on a worldwide basis has necessitated an urgent search for alternative energy sources to cater to the present day's demand. Another key reason to reduce our reliance on fossil fuels is the growing evidence of the global warming phenomena. Therefore, it is imperative to find alternative energy sources to cover the continuously increasing demand of energy while minimize the negative environmental impacts. Solar and wind energy systems are being considered as promising power generating sources due to their availability and topological advantages for local power generations in remote areas. Utilization of solar and wind energy has become increasingly significant, attractive and cost-effective, since the oil crises of early 1970s.

However, a drawback, common to solar and wind options, is their unpredictable nature and dependence on weather and climatic changes, and the variations of solar and wind energy may not match with the time distribution of load demand. Fortunately, the problems caused by the variable nature of these resources can be partially or wholly overcome by integrating these two energy resources in a proper combination, using the strengths of one source to overcome the weakness of the other. With the complementary characteristics between solar energy and wind energy for certain locations, the hybrid solar–wind power generation systems with storage banks offer a highly reliable source of power, which is suitable to electrical loads that need higher reliability. However, many works have been identified in hybrid systems where the different researchers have proposed different conventional and evolutionary algorithms to achieve the optimal size of the components used in hybrid systems. Different research activities have been carried out using conventional techniques such as graphical construction method, iterative method, trade off method and linear programming. The problem with conventional techniques is that they often trap in local minima. To overcome these shortcomings numerous meta-heuristic evolutionary algorithms, i.e., genetic algorithm, particle swarm optimization, ant and bee colony algorithm, harmony search, biogeography based optimization, etc. have been implemented in different hybrid systems. In recent years, a new trend has been observed where researchers are applying these evolutionary algorithms for optimal sizing of the hybrid energy system. To the best of authors knowledge, a very limited work is found, where the optimization of hybrid PV-wind-diesel generator along with the energy storage system has been explored. A swarm based meta-heuristic, artificial bee colony (ABC) algorithm has been applied to realize optimal configurations of the proposed system. The major factor which differentiates ABC algorithm from other algorithms (such as GA and PSO) is that it employs a lesser number of control parameters. Also, it has a good convergence accuracy and potential to provide optimal results, like other evolutionary algorithms.

2. OBJECTIVES

From the earlier mentioned introduction, it has been observed that there is a need for a hybrid system which consists of a PV, wind and Diesel generator along with an energy storage system especially in isolated or off-grid locations. The sizing of each equipment in any hybrid system is a challenging work. Despite works in literature under different perspectives, the proposed work focuses on the hybrid energy system which is a combination of PV, wind, Diesel Generator and energy storage. The optimal sizing of components for all the above hybrid systems has been identified by using either software tools or by conventional and evolutionary algorithms. But none of the researchers have worked on the optimal sizing of PV-wind-Diesel generator with battery bank as storage using evolutionary algorithms. The Diesel generator resources can be harnessed along with wind and solar sources to enhance the reliability of the hybrid system. Therefore, in this paper, an autonomous hybrid PV- wind-Diesel generator with battery system is proposed to fulfill the electrical demand of a typical village. A swarm based meta-heuristic, artificial bee colony (ABC) algorithm has been applied to realize optimal configurations of the proposed system. The major factor which differentiates ABC algorithm from other algorithms (such as GA and PSO) is that it employs a lesser number of control parameters. Also, it has a good convergence accuracy and potential to provide optimal results, like other evolutionary algorithms. The main objectives of this work are outlined as follows.

- To develop a mathematical model of an autonomous PV-wind diesel generator energy system with battery bank to provide electricity for an off-grid location.
- To deduce the optimal size of the components used in the proposed system with the least LCOE by minimizing the net present cost (NPC) of the system by applying swarm based ABC algorithm.

3. MATHEMATICAL MODELING

This work emphasizes on the formulation of a new hybrid system to supply the reliable power to off-grid or isolated locations.

Fig1. Different components of the proposed hybrid model.

The power generated by wind, solar and diesel generators is managed with the help of storage devices. As shown in Fig. 1, the load, wind turbines and biomass gasifier are connected to the AC bus. Moreover, solar PV panels and batteries are connected to the AC bus via converters. A charge controller is also deployed to maintain the smooth flow of power and limit the charging and discharging rate of batteries.

The proposed system is most suitable for off grid locations and agriculture based villages in developing countries where energy crisis is a major concern. This system will be helpful in reducing utility grid dependency as it is completely self sustaining with the renewable energy sources. This work mainly emphasizes on optimal sizing of each component, while guaranteeing the reliability of the system. The mathematical models of different components are discussed as follows:

a) Solar photovoltaic panel:

r

$$P_{sol}(t) = P_r^s f_{loss} \frac{G_h(t)}{G_S}$$

P^s :Rating of solar PV panel, f_{loss} : loss factor of solar PV panel, $G_h(t)$:hourly solar radiation incident at surface of solar PV panel (W/m^2), and G_S is the standard incident radiation ($1000 W/m^2$).

b) Wind Power Generation:

r

$$P_{wt}(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & V(t) \leq V_{cin} \text{ or } V(t) \geq V_{cot} \\ P_r^w & V_{rat} \leq V(t) \leq V_{cout} \\ P_r^w \frac{V(t)-V_{cin}}{V_{rat}-V_{cin}} & V_{cin} \leq V(t) \leq V_{rat} \end{cases}$$

P^w : Rating of single wind turbine,

V_{cin} : Cut in speed

V_{rat} : Rated wind speed

V_{cout} : Furlong Speed, $V(t)$: Wind speed at desired height

c) Diesel Generator

$$E_{dg} = P_{dg} (8760 * CUF) ;$$

P_{dg} : Rating of diesel generator, CUF: Capacity Utilization Factor, E_{dg} : Output electricity of a biomass gasifier.

d) Battery Bank:

$$\frac{SOC(t)}{SOC(t-1)} = \int_{T-1}^T \frac{P_b(t) \eta_{batt}}{V_{bus}} dt$$

V_{bus} : Voltage of bus, $P_b(t)$: battery's input/output power, η_{batt} : Round trip efficiency of battery.

e) Power Converter

$$\underline{P_{inv}(t) = P_L^m(t) / \eta_{inv}}$$

$P_{inv}(t)$: Inverter rating

$P^m(t)$: Peak load demand

η_{inv} : Efficiency of Inverter

4. OPERATIONAL STRATEGY

In case of any hybrid energy system, proper power management is required to achieve reliability of the system. In this system, diesel generators are kept on least priority, i.e. it is run when solar, wind and batteries are unable to meet the load demand.

Simplified steps of operational strategy are as follows:

- If the total power produced by solar PV panels and wind turbines is insufficient and also wind power is less than load, then demand can be served by renewable sources only. After satisfying the load, surplus power can be provided to the battery bank and is given as:

$$P_b(t) = P_{PV}(t) - [P_L(t) - P_w(t)]/\eta_{inv}$$

where $P_L(t)$ denotes load demand at any time and η_{inv} denotes the efficiency of the inverter. If $P_{sol}(t)$ is the power produced by an individual solar PV panel and N_{sol} is the total number of solar PV panels, then the total power produced by solar PV panels ($P_{PV}(t)$) is given as

$$P_{PV}(t) = P_{sol}(t)N_{sol}$$

Further, if P_{wt} is the power produced by an individual wind turbine and N_{wt} is the total number of wind turbines, then the total power generated by wind turbines ($P_w(t)$) can be given as,

$$P_w(t) = P_{wt}(t)N_{wt}$$

If power generated solely from wind turbines is enough to supply load demand, the remaining power (solar & wind) can be fed to the battery bank. The battery power in this case can be calculated as,

$$P_b(t) = [P_w(t) - P_L(t)]\eta_{rec} + P_{PV}(t)$$

$$P_{dump}(t) = P_b(t) - P_b^{max}(t)$$

- In both the above mentioned cases, if P_b is greater than the maximum allowable capacity of battery bank (P_b^{max}) then excess energy could be dumped or can be given to deferrable loads. Excessor dump energy is obtained as,
- If solar PV panels and wind turbines are not generating adequate power, then balance power can be supplied by the battery and is calculated as,

$$P_b(t) = [P_L(t) - P_w(t)]\eta_{inv} - P_{PV}(t)$$

- If solar and wind power are inadequate and batteries SOC min are also not able to produce the desired power to meet the load demand, then a Diesel generator supplies power to the load. Biomass gasifier can be used in two ways,
 - a) First, load following strategy, i.e. whenever it operates, it generates only required power to meet the primary load demand. The power generated by the biomass gasifier is calculated as.

$$P_{dg}(t) = P_L(t) - P_w(t) - P_{PV}(t)/\eta_{inv}$$

- b) In the second strategy, it operates at rated capacity or minimum load ratio. In case biomass gasifier is operating at rated capacity, the surplus power is used to charge the batteries and may be expressed as above.

5. OBJECTIVE FUNCTION AND CONSTRAINTS

The main motive of this study is to minimize total NPC of the proposed hybrid system while maintaining the optimal energy flow. For optimal configuration, four main decision factors, i.e., the number of wind turbines, solar PV panels,

batteries and, rating of diesel generators have been selected. For economic analysis, annualized system cost (ASC) concept is used. The result with least ASC is observed to be an optimal one while meeting all other constraints and parameters. The objective function considered is the total system cost, which consists of (i) total capital cost (ii) replacement cost and (iii) operational & maintenance cost of the components. Installation and civil works costs are incorporated in the capital costs of the components. The following function is considered as the main objective function which is to be minimized subject to constraints.

Minimize ASC:

$$= F(N_{sol}C_{sol} + N_{wt}C_{wind} + N_{batt}C_{batt} + P_{inv}C_{inv} + P_{dg} C_{dg})$$

where C_{sol} ; C_{wind} ; C_{batt} and C_{inv} are the cost of solar PV panel (per kW), wind turbine (per kW), battery (per unit) and inverter (per kW) respectively. C_{bmg} is the cost of biomass gasifier (per kW) and P_{bmg} is the rating of biomass gasifier. P_{inv} is the rating of the inverter.

The ASC of the installed component has several parts such as capital and installation cost (C_{acap}), replacement cost (C_{arep}), annual maintenance cost (C_m), operation cost (C_f) and salvage cost (C_{sal}). Further, total ASC of each component can be expressed as follows,

$$C_{sol} = C_{sol}^{acap} + C_{sol}^{arep} + C_{sol}^m - C_{sol}^{sal}$$

$$C_{wind} = C_{wind}^{acap} + C_{wind}^{arep} + C_{wind}^m - C_{wind}^{sal}$$

$$C_{batt} = C_{batt}^{acap} + C_{batt}^{arep} + C_{batt}^m - C_{batt}^{sal}$$

$$C_{DG} = C_{DG}^{acap} + C_{DG}^{arep} + C_{DG}^m + C_{DG}^f - C_{DG}^{sal}$$

$$C_{inv} = C_{inv}^{acap} + C_{inv}^{arep} + C_{inv}^m - C_{inv}^{sal}$$

The annualized cost of any component can be calculated with the help of a factor called capacity recovery factor (CRF). CRF is used to compute present value of money and can be given as,

$$CRF(i, N) = \frac{i(1+i)^N}{(1+i)^N - 1}$$

The optimal configuration is selected on the basis of LCOE and reliability. LCOE is declared as average price per kWh of the energy (useful) generated by the system and it can be given as,

$$LCOE = \frac{ASC(\$/year)}{\text{Total useful energy served}(kW h/year)}$$

6. ARTIFICIAL BEE COLONY ALGORITHM:

This emergent intelligent behavior in foraging bees can be summarized as follows:

Fig 2. Flowchart of the Artificial Bee Colony algorithm.

In a real bee colony, some tasks are performed by specialized individuals. These specialized bees try to maximize the nectar amount stored in the hive using efficient division of labour and self-organization. The Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) algorithm, proposed by Karaboga in 2005 for real-parameter optimization, is a recently introduced optimization algorithm which simulates the foraging behaviour of a bee colony.

The minimal model of swarm-intelligent forage selection in a honey bee colony which the ABC algorithm simulates consists of three kinds of bees: employed bees, onlooker bees and scout bees. Half of the colony consists of employed bees, and the other half includes onlooker bees. Employed bees are responsible for exploiting the nectar sources explored before and giving information to the waiting bees (onlooker bees) in the hive about the quality of the food source sites which they are exploiting. Onlooker bees wait in the hive and decide on a food source to exploit based on the information shared by the employed bees. Scouts either randomly search the environment in order to find a new food source depending on an internal motivation or based on possible external clues.

6. INPUT

Component	Parameter	Value	Unit
Wind turbine	Rated power (P_r^w)	1	kW
	Cut in speed (V_{cin})	3	m/s
	Cut out speed (V_{co})	20	m/s
	Rated wind speed (V_{rat})	5	m/s
	Capital cost (per kW)	2300	\$
	Replacement cost (per kW)	1500	\$
	O & M cost (per kW)	2	\$/yr
	Hub height	50	m
	Overall efficiency	26	%
	Life time	20	years
Solar PV	Rated power (P_r^s)	1	kW
	Derating factor (f_{loss})	88	%
	Capital cost (per kW)	1200	\$
	Replacement cost (per kW)	1200	\$
	O & M cost (per kW)	4	\$/yr
	Life time	20	years
Battery	Nominal capacity ($C_b(Ah)$)	360	Ah
	Nominal voltage (V_{batt})	6	V
	Max charging current (I_{max})	18	A
	Minimum state of charge (SOC_{min})	30	%
	Maximum state of charge (SOC_{max})	100	%
	Round trip efficiency (η_{batt})	92	%
	Capital cost (per unit)	167	\$
	Replacement cost (per unit)	67	\$
	O & M cost (per unit)	1.67	\$/yr
	Life time	5	years
Diesel generator	Rated power (P_{dg}^m)	50	kW
	Conversion efficiency (η_{dg})	21	%
	Capital cost (per kW)	2300	\$/kW
	Replacement cost (per kW)	1500	\$/kW
	O & M cost (per kW)	2	\$/yr
Converter	Life time	15,000	h
	Rated power	115	kW
	Rectifier(η_{rec}) and inverter(η_{inv}) efficiency	90	%
	Replacement cost (per kW)	127	\$/kW
Other	O & M cost (per kW)	1	\$/yr
	Life time	20	years
	Interest rate (i)	6	%
	Project life (N)	20	years
	Bus voltage (DC) (V_{bus})	120	V
	Batteries in string(N_{batt}^s)	20	units

Table 1. Technical and economical data of the components used in the proposed hybrid system ABC ALGORITHM.

ABC algorithm
Dimension of the problem (D): 3
Employed bees = onlooker bees: 20
Colony size (NP): 40
Food number: 20 (1/2 of the colony size)
Maximum cycle: 3000
Limit: 60

Table 2. Parameters of the ABC algorithm

Fig 4. Load demand (in Kw) vs. time (in hours)

Fig 6. Wind Speed (in m/s) vs. time (in hours)

7. .RESULTS

Fig. 7 Energy (in Kw) vs. time (in hours)

Fig. 8 State of Battery

Fig. 9: Variable load and renewable energy power generation

8. CONCLUSION

The experimental results were simulated using the ABC algorithm using the MATLAB 2018a program. After simulation, we have obtained the following output:-

Total Wind energy (KWh) = 4.2799×10^5
 Total Solar energy (KWh) = 1.6998×10^5
 Total DG Energy generation (KWh) = 1.4327×10^6
 Wasted Energy (KWh) = 3.5369×10^4
 LCOE_ = 0.4058 \$/kWh Total
 NPC = 5.7636×10^6 \$
 Annual cost = 8.0836×10^5 \$/yr
 Wind cost = 1.1842×10^5 \$/yr
 Solar cost = 5.8200×10^4 \$/yr
 DG cost = 6.2997×10^5 \$/yr
 Battery cost = 225.6498 \$/yr
 Inverter Total cost = 1.5422×10^3 \$/yr
 $B_{in} = 271.7212$
 $B_{out} = 245.606$

A hybrid energy system is a more reliable, economical and suitable source of electricity, particularly for off-grid locations. In this paper, a mathematical model has been developed to find the optimal size of components of a hybrid PV-wind-battery with diesel generator by applying the ABC algorithm. Initially, mathematical modeling of different components used in the study is discussed briefly, later on operational strategy and implementation steps of the ABC algorithm has been presented.

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